

Loss of the incretin effect in type 2 diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis – Supplementary Methods and Results

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Supplementary Methods

Data sources, search string and selection criteria

Eligible studies have been identified by electronic search in PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science. The search string was (“oral glucose” AND (isoglycemic OR isoglycaemic)) OR (OGTT AND “incretin effect”). The last search update was 15 May 2021. The search retrieved 183 publications; further 6 articles were added based on personal knowledge or the citations of the selected publications. Tables S1-S3 show the inclusion and exclusion criteria and the 189 retrieved publications, indicating the source and the reasons for exclusion. Figure 1 in the main text shows the PRISMA diagram of the publication screening.

From the studies satisfying the inclusion criteria, subject groups with particular characteristics were excluded as in the Methods section in the main text. Details of the exclusion are reported in Table S4.

Data extraction and quality assessment

Relevant data were extracted from the published tables, if available, or from the scanned figures using custom software for manual digitalization.

Data were converted to homogeneous units using standard conversion factors. For GIP and GLP-1, only the concentrations of the total hormones were extracted and the conversion factors from pg/mL to pmol/L were 0.2106 for GIP and 0.3236 for GLP-1. A few measures obtained with old assays (four subject groups for GIP (1-3) and one for GLP-1 (3)) were rescaled as previously described (4). GIP and GLP-1 data were discarded in Pontikis et al. (5) and insulin AUCs in Galderisi et al. (6), as much higher compared to the rest of the studies.

To report areas under the curves (AUC) homogeneously, we have calculated incremental AUCs from absolute AUCs (or absolute AUCs from incremental AUCs) using the basal values, when possible. To partially account for the different test durations, mean values (as AUC/time) were used consistently.

Data distributions and relationships were extensively checked to identify possible recording errors. In a few cases, anomalous values were identified as originating from data reported incorrectly in the publication (e.g. an AUC mean reported as absolute AUC) and corrected accordingly.

Assessment of the incretin effect

The methods used to calculate the incretin effect (IE) were not homogeneous across the included studies. In our analysis, we chose to use as a reference method the IE index calculated from incremental (above baseline) AUCs (iAUC) as:

$$iIE_0 = \frac{iAUC_{OGTT} - iAUC_{IGI}}{iAUC_{OGTT}}$$

This index (iIE_0) uses the OGTT iAUC at the denominator (hence the subscript “O”), is expressed in percent and is calculated from insulin and C-peptide.

The alternative IE index based on absolute AUCs was as frequently used as the reference index in the included studies, while the use of the IIGI AUC at the denominator was less common. Here we make the relationships between IE indices explicit.

Denoting as \overline{AUC} the absolute AUC mean (i.e. AUC/time), with $i\overline{AUC}$ the incremental AUC mean, and with B the basal value, the following relationships hold:

$$i\overline{AUC}_{IIGI} = \overline{AUC}_{IIGI} - B_{IIGI}$$

$$i\overline{AUC}_{OGTT} = \overline{AUC}_{OGTT} - B_{OGTT}$$

The reference incretin effect (iIE_0) can be obtained from the AUC means with same equation used for the AUCs, i.e.:

$$iIE_0 = \frac{i\overline{AUC}_{OGTT} - i\overline{AUC}_{IIGI}}{i\overline{AUC}_{OGTT}}$$

With simple algebraic manipulations, it can be shown that incretin effect calculated using the IIGI at the denominator (iIE_1) is:

$$iIE_1 = \frac{iIE_0}{1 - iIE_0}$$

An analogous relationship holds for the index based on absolute AUCs. The IE indices iIE_1 and iIE_0 are thus nonlinearly related. Assuming that the OGTT response is greater or equal to IIGI response, the iIE_0 range is 0-1 (or 0-100%), while the iIE_1 range is 0- ∞ .

The relationship between the reference method based on incremental AUCs (iIE_0) and the method using absolute AUCs (IE_0), both using the OGTT at the denominator, is:

$$iIE_0 = IE_0 \left(1 + \frac{B_{OGTT}}{i\overline{AUC}_{OGTT}} \right)$$

This equations assumes an ideal condition of equal basal values in the OGTT and IIGI ($B_{OGTT}=B_{IIGI}$). In the hypothesis that $i\overline{AUC}_{OGTT} > 0$ (positive incremental response during the OGTT), $iIE_0 > IE_0$. The two indices are thus not equivalent. However, the nature of the relationship suggests that the two indices could be linearly related.

We have thus relied on individual data from our previous studies including 75 subjects with glucose tolerance spanning from NGT to T2D (7-9) to verify the relationship between iIE_0 and IE_0 , for both insulin and C-peptide. We show that iIE_0 and IE_0 are linearly related (Figure S2 for the index based on insulin). The regression equations were $iIE_0 = 1.1323 \cdot IE_0 + 4.1427$ ($R^2=0.93$, $p<0.0001$) and $iIE_0 = 1.0953 \cdot IE_0 + 10.691$ ($R^2=0.85$, $p<0.0001$), for IE calculated from insulin and C-peptide, respectively, and expressed in percent. These relationships confirm the theoretical result showing that $iIE_0 > IE_0$.

These equations were used to transform IE calculated from the absolute AUCs in the studies of the systematic review, in order to homogenize the two methods on the scale of reference IE index. The standard deviation of the original IE_0 was accordingly multiplied by 1.1323 for insulin and by 1.0953 for C-peptide, to obtain the standard deviation of the transformed iIE_0 .

In contrast, as the index using the OGTT AUC (or $iAUC$) at the denominator is not linearly related to the reference index, the published data cannot be transformed into a scale homogeneous with the reference index and the studies employing this approach were excluded. An exception were the studies for which we had access to the individual data (7-9), where we could recalculate the incretin effect using the reference method.

References

1. Nauck MA, Homberger E, Siegel EG, Allen RC, Eaton RP, Ebert R, Creutzfeldt W: Incretin effects of increasing glucose loads in man calculated from venous insulin and c-peptide responses. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 63:492-498, 1986
2. Nauck M, Stöckmann F, Ebert R, Creutzfeldt W: Reduced incretin effect in type 2 (non-insulin-dependent) diabetes. *Diabetologia* 29:46-52, 1986
3. Nauck MA, Bartels E, Orskov C, Ebert R, Creutzfeldt W: Additive insulinotropic effects of exogenous synthetic human gastric inhibitory polypeptide and glucagon-like peptide-1-(7-36) amide infused at near-physiological insulinotropic hormone and glucose concentrations. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 76:912-917, 1993
4. Grespan E, Giorgino T, Natali A, Ferrannini E, Mari A: Different mechanisms of GIP and GLP-1 action explain their different therapeutic efficacy in type 2 diabetes. *Metabolism: clinical and experimental*:154415, 2021
5. Pontikis C, Yavropoulou MP, Toulis KA, Kotsa K, Kazakos K, Papazisi A, Gotzamani-Psarakou A, Yovos JG: The incretin effect and secretion in obese and lean women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a pilot study. *J Womens Health (Larchmt)* 20:971-976, 2011
6. Galderisi A, Trico D, Pierpont B, Shabanova V, Samuels S, Dalla Man C, Galuppo B, Santoro N, Caprio S: A Reduced Incretin Effect Mediated by the rs7903146 Variant in the TCF7L2 Gene Is an Early Marker of beta-Cell Dysfunction in Obese Youth. *Diabetes Care* 43:2553-2563, 2020
7. Muscelli E, Mari A, Natali A, Astiarraga BD, Camastra S, Frascerra S, Holst JJ, Ferrannini E: Impact of incretin hormones on beta-cell function in subjects with normal or impaired glucose tolerance. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* 291:E1144-1150, 2006
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9. Astiarraga B, Chueire VB, Souza AL, Pereira-Moreira R, Monte Alegre S, Natali A, Tura A, Mari A, Ferrannini E, Muscelli E: Effects of acute NEFA manipulation on incretin-induced insulin secretion in participants with and without type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia* 61:1829-1837, 2018

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Classification	Description	Exclusion
No gold standard protocol	Study does not include OGTT+IIGI	yes
Secondary study	Data are derived from other previously published studies with gold standard protocol, included in the search	yes
IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used, but IE is not reported (usually because not the main goal)	yes
Review	Review or thesis, without original data	yes
Included	Study included in the analysis	no
No human	Study without relevant data in humans	yes
Nonstandard IE	Nonstandard IE, which cannot be transformed to standard	yes
Trial description	Description of a trial, with no relevant data	yes
Not English	Paper not in English for which the inclusion criteria cannot be determined from the abstract	yes
Abstract or Letter	Abstract only or letter, with no data (applies to Scopus only)	yes

Table S2. List of publications retrieved by the systematic search and screened for inclusion.

Study	Source	Inclusion/Exclusion	Comments
Andersen1997	P	No gold standard protocol	
Andersen1999	P	No gold standard protocol	
Anderwald2007	P	No gold standard protocol	
Anderwald2008	P	No gold standard protocol	
Anderwald2011	P	No gold standard protocol	
Anderwald2012	P	No gold standard protocol	
Astiarraga2018	P	Included	
Astiarraga2020	O	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Aulinger2014	P	Nonstandard IE	IE is calculated as absolute difference.
Aulinger2016	P	Included	
Bagger2011	P	Included	
Bagger2014	P	Secondary study	From Bagger 2011.
Bergmann2019JCEM	P	IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used. Part of the GASOLIN study. Data are reported elsewhere.
Bergmann2019Diabetologia	S	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in the paper.
Bose2010	P	Included	
Bourron2012	P	No gold standard protocol	
Brundin1999	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Burattini2012	P	Secondary study	Mean published data from Muscelli 2006 and Nauck 2004.
Calanna2014	P	Included	
Camacho2004	W	No human	
Campioni2007	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Ceriello2011	P	No gold standard protocol	
Chen2010	P	No human	
Choi2016	P	IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used, but the goal is glucose matching, not IE.
Christoffersen2009	P	No human	
Cree-Green2018	S	No gold standard protocol	
Creutzfeldt1983	P	Nonstandard IE	
Creutzfeldt1985SchwMedWoch	P	Not English	German, likely a review.
Creutzfeldt1985Diabetologia	O	IE not reported	Review with data but no IE. Control group cited

Study	Source	Inclusion/Exclusion	Comments
			in Nauck1993ActaDiabetol.
Creutzfeldt2001	P	Review	
Davis2012	P	No human	
DeGaetano2013	P	No gold standard protocol	
Dela2019	S	No gold standard protocol	
Deng2015	P	No gold standard protocol	
Dupre1991	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate (glucose not well matched) but IE is not reported in paper.
Dupré1993	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Dutia2014	P	Included	
Ebert1980	P	No gold standard protocol	
Edgerton2019	P	No human	
Eriksen2015	P	No gold standard protocol	
Fernandes2019	P	No gold standard protocol	
Foghsgaard2013	P	Trial description	Describes trial for Foghsgaard 2019.
Foghsgaard2017	P	Included	
Fotheringham2020	P	Secondary study	Data from Bagger 2011.
Frost2019	P	IE not reported	IE is reported, but not the IE SD.
Füessl1990	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Galderisi2020	P	Included	
Gilor2011	P	No human	
Greenbaum1999	S	Abstract or Letter	
Greenbaum2002	P	Included	T1D & NGT controls.
Gregory2019	P	No gold standard protocol	
Grespan2021	P	No gold standard protocol	
Gyldenløve2015	P	Included	
Halperin2012	S	No gold standard protocol	
Hansen2010	P	Included	
Hare2010DanMedBull	P	Review	Dan Med Bull. Review for a thesis.
Hare2010AJP	P	Included	T1D (undetectable C-peptide) and NGT controls.
Himpens2016	P	Included	
Holst2011	P	Review	
Holter2017	O	Included	
Hong2013	P	No gold standard protocol	
Huang2013	P	No human	
Idorn2013	P	Included	
Ishikawa2015	P	No human	
Jacob1996	P	No gold standard protocol	
Jauslin2007	P	No gold standard protocol	
Jensen1976	P	No human	
Jensen2012	P	Included	
Jhuma2017	S	No gold standard protocol	
Junker2016	P	Included	
Junker2015	P	Included	
Kahleova2014	P	No gold standard protocol	
Kartono2021	S	No gold standard protocol	
Kashyap2010	P	No gold standard protocol	
Kazafeos2011	P	Review	
Kazakos2008	P	No gold standard protocol	IIGI has a fixed glucose dose, not a clamp.
Kelly2009	P	No gold standard protocol	
Kim2014	P	Included	
Kindmark2001	W	No gold standard protocol	
Kissler1999	P	No human	
Kissler2000	P	No human	
Knop2007Diabetes	P	Included	
Knop2007Diabetologia	P	Included	
Knop2007RegulPept	P	No gold standard protocol	
Knop2009	P	Review	

Study	Source	Inclusion/Exclusion	Comments
Knop2012	P	Included	
Knop2018	P	Review	
Köhler1992	P	No human	
Kosinski2013	P	Included	
Laferrère2007	P	Included	
Laferrère2008	P	Included	
Laferrère2009	P	Review	
Laferrère2016	P	Review	
Lauritsen1978	O	Nonstandard IE	
Lauritsen1980a	P	Nonstandard IE	
Lauritsen1980b	P	Nonstandard IE	
Lauritsen1982	P	Nonstandard IE	
Lee2010	P	No gold standard protocol	
Lee2014	P	Included	
Lencioni2011	P	No gold standard protocol	
Lund2011	P	Included	
Lund2014	P	Included	
Lund2016Diabetes	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Lund2016JCEM	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Lund2017	P	Review	Dan Med J. Review for a thesis.
Lundkvist2019	P	No gold standard protocol	
Maagensen2018	P	Secondary study	From Junker 2016.
Maekawa2017	P	No human	
Manning2013	P	IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used (glucose not well matched) but IE is not reported in paper.
Marathe2020	O	No gold standard protocol	
Mari2013	P	Secondary study	From Bagger 2011.
Marini2012	P	No gold standard protocol	IE from OGTT & IVGTT.
Mathiesen2020	P	Secondary study	Data from various studies.
Meier2007	P	IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used. Results from Nauck 2004.
Meister1988	P	No human	
Meister1990	P	No human	
Michaliszyn2014	P	No gold standard protocol	
Mingrone2020	P	No gold standard protocol	Data potentially allow quasi-standard IE calculation, but IE is not reported.
Morettini2011	S	Secondary study	
Muscelli2006	P	Included	
Muscelli2008	P	Included	
Muscelli2012	P	No gold standard protocol	Gold standard approach is used but with MMTT.
Musso2009AJCN	P	No gold standard protocol	Protocol uses OGTT+IVGTT.
Musso2009Hepatology	P	No gold standard protocol	Protocol uses OGTT+IVGTT.
Musso2011	P	No gold standard protocol	Protocol uses OGTT+IVGTT.
Musso2017	P	No gold standard protocol	Protocol uses OGTT+IVGTT.
Nauck1986JCEM	P	Included	
Nauck1986Diabetologia	P	Included	
Nauck1993JCEM	P	Included	
Nauck1993ActaDiabetol	P	Included	
Nauck2004	P	Included	
Nielsen2013	P	Included	
Nielsen2015	P	Included	
Nielsen2016	P	Included	
Novaes2015	P	Included	
Oda2013	P	No human	
Oh2014	P	Included	
Oh2016	P	Review	
Olsen1999	P	No gold standard protocol	
Olsen2000	P	No gold standard protocol	

Study	Source	Inclusion/Exclusion	Comments
Østoft2014	P	Included	
Østoft2015	P	Review	Dan Med J. Review for a thesis.
Pacini2012	P	No gold standard protocol	IE from OGTT & IVGTT.
Patto1993	P	No gold standard protocol	Protocol uses OGTT+IVGTT.
Pelikánová1994	P	No gold standard protocol	
Peyot2004	P	No human	
Placzowska2017	S	No gold standard protocol	
Plamboeck2013	P	Included	
Pontikis2011	P	Included	
Pontillo2018	S	Abstract or Letter	
Pratley2009	P	Review	
Prévost2019	P	No human	
Promintzer-Schifferl2011	P	No gold standard protocol	
Rhee2014	P	Included	
Salehi2012	P	No gold standard protocol	
Salinari2017	P	IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used. Results from Nauck 2004.
Sass2020	O	Secondary study	Data from Hare 2010 AJP.
Saxena2010	P	Nonstandard IE	IE from OGTT & IVGTT.
Scrocchi1998Endocrinology	P	No human	
Scrocchi1998Diabetes	P	No human	
Shah2019	P	Secondary study	IE not reported. Primary studies: Holter 2017, Dutia 2014.
Shcherbina2018	P	No gold standard protocol	
Siegel1998	W	No gold standard protocol	
Silber2010	P	No gold standard protocol	
Silfia2015	S	No gold standard protocol	Secondary study. Original data from PhD thesis.
Simon2015	P	IE not reported	Gold standard protocol is used but standard IE absent, also in supplement.
Sindelka2001	P	No gold standard protocol	
Skrha2010	P	No gold standard protocol	
Sonne2014	P	Secondary study	Data from Lund 2011 for the gold standard protocol. Ref 14 of the paper has no IIGI.
Stadler2009	P	No gold standard protocol	
Starup-Linde2018	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Svendsen2009	P	No gold standard protocol	
Terry2014	P	No human	
Thomaseth2007	P	No gold standard protocol	
Toft-Nielsen2001	P	No gold standard protocol	
Trahair2017	P	No gold standard protocol	
Tura2014	P	Secondary study	Data from Muscelli 2006 & 2008.
Tura2017	P	Secondary study	Data from Bagger 2011.
Vaag1999	S	Review	Danish Medical Bulletin.
Vahidi2016	P	Secondary study	Data from Knop 2007 Diabetes.
vanderBurg1996	P	No human	
Vardarli2011	P	Included	
Vardarli2014	P	Included	
Veedfald2015	P	Secondary study	IE in Plamboeck 2013.
Villareal2010	P	Included	
Wang2017	P	No human	
Westberg-Rasmussen2017	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Yan2017	P	IE not reported	Protocol would be appropriate but IE is not reported in paper.
Yeow2017	P	No gold standard protocol	

Source: P = PubMed; S = Scopus; W = Web of Science; O = other sources (personal knowledge, publication cited in relevant studies).

Table S3. Bibliographic data of the screened publications.

Study	Bibliographic data
Andersen1997	Andersen UB, Dige-Petersen H, Frandsen EK, Ibsen H, Vølund A: Basal insulin-level oscillations in normotensive individuals with genetic predisposition to essential hypertension exhibit an irregular pattern. <i>J Hypertens</i> 15:1167-1173, 1997
Andersen1999	Andersen UB, Dige-Petersen H, Ibsen H, Skøtt P, Bruun NE, Vestergaard H, Christiansen C: Insulin resistance, exercise capacity and body composition in subjects with two hypertensive parents. <i>J Hypertens</i> 17:1273-1280, 1999
Anderwald2007	Anderwald C, Anderwald-Stadler M, Promintzer M, Prager G, Mandl M, Nowotny P, Bischof MG, Wolzt M, Ludvik B, Kästenbauer T, Pacini G, Luger A, Krebs M: The Clamp-Like Index: a novel and highly sensitive insulin sensitivity index to calculate hyperinsulinemic clamp glucose infusion rates from oral glucose tolerance tests in nondiabetic subjects. <i>Diabetes Care</i> 30:2374-2380, 2007
Anderwald2008	Anderwald C, Pfeiler G, Nowotny P, Anderwald-Stadler M, Krebs M, Bischof MG, Kozakova M, Luger A, Pacini G, Roden M, Waldhäusl W: Glucose turnover and intima media thickness of internal carotid artery in type 2 diabetes offspring. <i>Eur J Clin Invest</i> 38:227-237, 2008
Anderwald2011	Anderwald C, Gastaldelli A, Tura A, Krebs M, Promintzer-Schifferl M, Kautzky-Willer A, Stadler M, DeFronzo RA, Pacini G, Bischof MG: Mechanism and effects of glucose absorption during an oral glucose tolerance test among females and males. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab</i> 96:515-524, 2011
Anderwald2012	Anderwald CH, Tura A, Promintzer-Schifferl M, Prager G, Stadler M, Ludvik B, Esterbauer H, Bischof MG, Luger A, Pacini G, Krebs M: Alterations in gastrointestinal, endocrine, and metabolic processes after bariatric Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery. <i>Diabetes Care</i> 35:2580-2587, 2012
Astiarraga2018	Astiarraga B, Chueire VB, Souza AL, Pereira-Moreira R, Monte Alegre S, Natali A, Tura A, Mari A, Ferrannini E, Muscelli E: Effects of acute NEFA manipulation on incretin-induced insulin secretion in participants with and without type 2 diabetes. <i>Diabetologia</i> 61:1829-1837, 2018
Astiarraga2020	Astiarraga B, Martínez L, Ceperuelo-Mallafré V, Llauradó G, Terrón-Puig M, Mar Rodríguez M, Casajoana A, Pellitero S, Megía A, Vilarrasa N, Vendrell J, Fernández-Veledo S: Impaired Succinate Response to a Mixed Meal in Obesity and Type 2 Diabetes Is Normalized After Metabolic Surgery. <i>Diabetes Care</i> , 2020
Aulinger2014	Aulinger BA, Bedorf A, Kutscherauer G, de Heer J, Holst JJ, Göke B, Schirra J: Defining the role of GLP-1 in the enteroinsular axis in type 2 diabetes using DPP-4 inhibition and GLP-1 receptor blockade. <i>Diabetes</i> 63:1079-1092, 2014
Aulinger2016	Aulinger BA, Vahl TP, Prigeon RL, D'Alessio DA, Elder DA: The incretin effect in obese adolescents with and without type 2 diabetes: impaired or intact? <i>Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab</i> 310:E774-781, 2016
Bagger2011	Bagger JI, Knop FK, Lund A, Vestergaard H, Holst JJ, Vilsbøll T: Impaired regulation of the incretin effect in patients with type 2 diabetes. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab</i> 96:737-745, 2011
Bagger2014	Bagger JI, Knop FK, Lund A, Holst JJ, Vilsbøll T: Glucagon responses to increasing oral loads of glucose and corresponding isoglycaemic intravenous glucose infusions in patients with type 2 diabetes and healthy individuals. <i>Diabetologia</i> 57:1720-1725, 2014
Bergmann2019JCEM	Bergmann NC, Lund A, Gasbjerg LS, Jørgensen NR, Jessen L, Hartmann B, Holst JJ, Christensen MB, Vilsbøll T, Knop FK: Separate and Combined Effects of GIP and GLP-1 Infusions on Bone Metabolism in Overweight Men Without Diabetes. <i>J Clin Endocrinol Metab</i> 104:2953-2960, 2019
Bergmann2019Diabetologia	Bergmann NC, Lund A, Gasbjerg LS, Meessen ECE, Andersen MM, Bergmann S, Hartmann B, Holst JJ, Jessen L, Christensen MB, Vilsbøll T, Knop FK: Effects of combined GIP and GLP-1 infusion on energy intake, appetite and energy expenditure in overweight/obese individuals: a randomised, crossover study. <i>Diabetologia</i> 62:665-675, 2019
Bose2010	Bose M, Teixeira J, Olivan B, Bawa B, Arias S, Machineni S, Pi-Sunyer FX, Scherer PE, Laferrère B: Weight loss and incretin responsiveness improve glucose control independently after gastric bypass surgery. <i>J Diabetes</i> 2:47-55, 2010
Bourron2012	Bourron O, Chebbi F, Halbron M, Saint-Martin C, Bellanné-Chantelot C, Abed A, Charbit B, Magnan C, Lacorte JM, Hartemann A: Incretin effect of glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonist is preserved in presence of ABCC8/SUR1 mutation in β -cell. <i>Diabetes Care</i> 35:e76, 2012
Brundin1999	Brundin T: Splanchnic and extrasplanchnic extraction of insulin following oral and intravenous glucose loads. <i>Clin Sci (Lond)</i> 97:429-436, 1999

Study	Bibliographic data
Burattini2012	Burattini R, Morettini M: Identification of an integrated mathematical model of standard oral glucose tolerance test for characterization of insulin potentiation in health. <i>Comput Methods Programs Biomed</i> 107:248-261, 2012
Calanna2014	Calanna S, Scicali R, Di Pino A, Knop FK, Piro S, Rabuazzo AM, Purrello F: Alpha- and beta-cell abnormalities in haemoglobin A1c-defined prediabetes and type 2 diabetes. <i>Acta Diabetol</i> 51:567-575, 2014
Camacho2004	Camacho RC, Denny JC, Pencek RR, Koyama Y, Lacy DB, James FD, Wasserman DH: Portal venous hyperinsulinemia does not stimulate gut glucose absorption in the conscious dog. <i>Metabolism: clinical and experimental</i> 53:1290-1295, 2004
Campioni2007	Campioni M, Toffolo G, Shuster LT, Service FJ, Rizza RA, Cobelli C: Incretin effect potentiates beta-cell responsivity to glucose as well as to its rate of change: OGTT and matched intravenous study. <i>Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab</i> 292:E54-60, 2007
Ceriello2011	Ceriello A, Esposito K, Testa R, Bonfigli AR, Marra M, Giugliano D: The possible protective role of glucagon-like peptide 1 on endothelium during the meal and evidence for an "endothelial resistance" to glucagon-like peptide 1 in diabetes. <i>Diabetes Care</i> 34:697-702, 2011
Chen2010	Chen LL, Yang WH, Zheng J, Hu X, Kong W, Zhang HH: Effect of catch-up growth after food restriction on the entero-insular axis in rats. <i>Nutr Metab (Lond)</i> 7:45, 2010
Choi2016	Choi K, Lee JC, Oh TJ, Kim M, Kim HC, Cho YM, Kim S: A Computational Method to Determine Glucose Infusion Rates for Isoglycemic Intravenous Glucose Infusion Study. <i>IEEE J Biomed Health Inform</i> 20:4-10, 2016
Christoffersen2009	Christoffersen B, Ribel U, Raun K, Golozoubova V, Pacini G: Evaluation of different methods for assessment of insulin sensitivity in Gottingen minipigs: introduction of a new, simpler method. <i>Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol</i> 297:R1195-1201, 2009
Cree-Green2018	Cree-Green M, Xie D, Rahat H, Garcia-Reyes Y, Bergman BC, Scherzinger A, Behn CD, Chan CL, Kelsey MM, Pyle L, Nadeau KJ: Oral glucose tolerance test glucose peak time is most predictive of prediabetes and hepatic steatosis in obese girls. <i>Journal of the Endocrine Society</i> 2:547-562, 2018
Creutzfeldt1983	Creutzfeldt W, Ebert R, Nauck M, Stöckmann F: Disturbances of the entero-insular axis. <i>Scand J Gastroenterol Suppl</i> 82:111-119, 1983
Creutzfeldt1985SchwMedWoch	Creutzfeldt W: [Physiology and pathology of the entero-insular axis]. <i>Schweiz Med Wochenschr</i> 115:970-973, 1985
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Study	Bibliographic data
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Table S4. Exclusion of subject groups from the analysis. Muscelli2008 merges two studies (Refs. 4-5 above in the Supplement), as some subject groups are in common.

Study	Excluded groups ¹
Astiarraga2018	NGT with intralipid infusion; T2D with acipimox administration
Aulinger2016	None
Bagger2011	None
Bose2010	T2D post GBP
Calanna2014	None
Dutia2014	T2D post RYGB
Foghsgaard2017	None
Galderisi2020	NGT with high risk genetic variants
Greenbaum2002	None
Gyldenlove2015	NGT with psoriasis
Hansen2010	NGT post prednisolone, fat diet and inactivity
Hare2010AJP	T1D without residual insulin secretion
Himpens2016	Surgical patients (RYGB & OLAGB)
Holter2017	Post-surgery (RYGB & LAGB)
Idorn2013	End stage renal disease, both NGT and IGT
Jensen2012	Post dexamethasone
Junker2015	Nondiabetic cirrhotic patients
Junker2016	NAFLD patients
Kim2014	None
Knop2007Diabetes	NGT & T2D with chronic pancreatitis
Knop2007Diabetologia	None
Knop2012	None
Kosinski2013	None
LaFerrere2007	Post RYGB (Nondiabetic & T2D)
LaFerrere2008	Post GBP and diet
Lee2014	Post-surgery (SG & SAGB)
Lund2011	None
Lund2014	None
Muscelli2008	None
Nauck1986Diabetologia	None
Nauck1986JCEM	None
Nauck1993ActaDiabetol	NGT with kidney transplantation; T1D with pancreas-kidney transplantation
Nauck1993JCEM	None
Nauck2004	None
Nielsen2013	TNF-alpha infusion
Nielsen2015	Critically ill patients
Nielsen2016	Post bed rest
Novaes2015	Post BPD
Oh2014	None
Ostoft2014	MODY2 and MODY3
Plamboeck2013	Truncally vagotomized (also with DPP-4 inhibitors)
Pontikis2011	PCOS
Rhee2014	Post sitagliptin
Vardarli2011	Post vildagliptin
Vardarli2014	Post metformin/sitagliptin
Villareal2010	NGT with high risk genetic variants

¹NGT, normal glucose tolerance; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; T2D, type 2 diabetes; T1D, type 1 diabetes; MODY2, GCK-diabetes; MODY3, HNF1A-diabetes; NAFLD, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease; PCOS, polycystic ovary syndrome; LAGB, laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding; RYGB, Roux-en-Y gastric bypass; GBP, gastric bypass; SAGB, single anastomosis gastric bypass; OLAGB, omega loop gastric bypass; SG: sleeve gastrectomy; BPD, bilio-pancreatic diversion.

Table S5. Main characteristics of the included studies. For each study, data are provided for the glucose tolerance groups separately. Excluded subject groups (Table S4) are not shown. The IGT subject group in Foghsgaard2017 was excluded from the comparison between IE calculated from insulin and C-peptide, as C-peptide was missing. Muscelli2008 merges two studies (Refs. 4-5 above in the Supplement), as some subject groups are in common. Study Age, BMI and T2D duration shown in the table are means or medians in the subject group.

Study	Glucose tolerance ¹	Specific group characteristics ²	N	Sex (M/F)	Age (years)	BMI (kg/m ²)	T2D duration (months)	Incretin effect method ³
Astiarraga2018	NGT		10	4/6	34	23.8		tAUC
Astiarraga2018	T2D		13	10/3	55	32.8	90	tAUC
Aulinger2016	NGT	Lean	8	5/3	26.5	24.8		iAUC
Aulinger2016	NGT	Obese	11	3/8	17.7	42.1		iAUC
Aulinger2016	T2D	Obese	10	2/8	18	37.7	48	iAUC
Bagger2011	NGT		8	3/5	57	29		tAUC
Bagger2011	T2D		8	3/5	57	29	8	tAUC
Bose2010	NGT		8	0/8	37	45.1		tAUC
Bose2010	T2D		11	0/11	43	45.1	26.5	tAUC
Calanna2014	NGT		10	4/6	49.4	29.6		tAUC
Calanna2014	IGT	IGT from HbA1c	10	7/3	50.6	30.3		tAUC
Calanna2014	T2D		8	5/3	53.9	30.4		tAUC
Dutia2014	NGT	Lean	7		35.4	23.5		tAUC
Dutia2014	NGT	Obese	11		36.3	44.7		tAUC
Dutia2014	T2D	Obese	16		47.1	43.9	36	tAUC
Foghsgaard2017	NGT		15	0/15	39.2	28.8		iAUC
Foghsgaard2017	NGT	Previous GDM	39	0/39	39.5	31		iAUC
Foghsgaard2017	IGT	Previous GDM	63	0/63	38.3	32.1		iAUC
Galderisi2020	NGT	Low risk genetic variants	21	12/9	16	37		tAUC
Greenbaum2002	NGT	Increased T1D risk	14		26.8	20.2		iAUC
Gyldenlove2015	NGT		12	8/4	52.5	25.8		tAUC
Hansen2010	NGT		10	10/0	24	23		iAUC
Hare2010AJP	NGT		8	8/0	28	24		tAUC
Himpens2016	NGT		14	3/11	31.9	22.4		tAUC
Holter2017	T2D	Pre LAGB	12		48.5	43.4	35.7	tAUC
Holter2017	T2D	Pre RYGB	26		43.7	44.6	29.6	tAUC
Idorn2013	NGT		11	7/4	47.7	22.2		tAUC
Jensen2012	NGT	NGT after dexamethasone	10	6/4	27	23		iAUC
Jensen2012	NGT	IGT after dexamethasone	11	6/5	29	25		iAUC
Junker2015	NGT		15	10/5	57	29		iAUC
Junker2016	NGT		10		57	29		iAUC
Junker2016	T2D		8		59	27	52	iAUC
Kim2014	NGT		8	6/2	43.6	21.9		iAUC
Knop2007Diabetes	NGT		8	6/2	57	22		iAUC
Knop2007Diabetes	T2D		8	6/2	62	24		iAUC
Knop2007Diabetologia	NGT		10	8/2	58	23.1		iAUC
Knop2007Diabetologia	T2D		10	8/2	62	23.3	61	iAUC
Knop2012	NGT	Lean	8	8/0	59	23		tAUC
Knop2012	T2D	Lean	8		62	24	76	tAUC
Knop2012	NGT	Obese	8	8/0	58	35		tAUC
Knop2012	T2D	Obese	8	8/0	61	37	55	tAUC
Kosinski2013	NGT	Third trimester	8	0/8	29	25.7		iAUC
Kosinski2013	NGT	Post partum	8	0/8	29	25.7		iAUC
Kosinski2013	T2D	Third trimester	10	0/10	30	25.3		iAUC
Kosinski2013	NGT	Post partum (previous GDM)	10	0/10	30	25.3		iAUC
LaFerrere2007	NGT		7		38.9	37.1		tAUC
LaFerrere2007	T2D		8	0/8	44.8	43.6	20.1	tAUC
LaFerrere2008	T2D	Before GBP	10	0/10	46.8	43.3	22.2	tAUC
LaFerrere2008	T2D	Before diet	9	0/9	44.6	43.3	41.4	tAUC
Lee2014	T2D	Pre SAGB	30	8/22	44.6	30	69.6	tAUC
Lee2014	T2D	Pre GB	30	8/22	46.4	31	82.8	tAUC

Study	Glucose tolerance ¹	Specific group characteristics ²	N	Sex (M/F)	Age (years)	BMI (kg/m ²)	T2D duration (months)	Incretin effect method ³
Lund2011	T2D		10	4/6	51	33.2	58	tAUC
Lund2014	NGT	Trained	11	11/0	25	23		tAUC
Lund2014	NGT	Untrained	10	10/0	25	22		tAUC
Muscelli2008	NGT		24	10/14	41	33.1		iAUC
Muscelli2008	IGT		17	5/12	47	35.9		iAUC
Muscelli2008	T2D		10	9/1	50	35.5		iAUC
Nauck1986Diabetologia	NGT		8	5/3	56	23.6		iAUC
Nauck1986Diabetologia	T2D		14	7/7	61	25.2	84	iAUC
Nauck1986JCEM	NGT		6	5/1	30.5	23		iAUC
Nauck1993JCEM	NGT		8	8/0	25	24		tAUC
Nauck2004	NGT		10	6/4	45	26.1		iAUC
Nauck2004	NGT	T2D relatives	16	4/12	50	26.1		iAUC
Nielsen2013	NGT		10	10/0	24	24.7		tAUC
Nielsen2015	NGT		8	4/4	66.5	24.7		iAUC
Nielsen2016	NGT		10	10/0	23	24.5		iAUC
Novaes2015	NGT		13	0/13	39	23.4		tAUC
Novaes2015	T2D		10	0/10	47	35.8	36	tAUC
Oh2014	NGT	Korean subjects	14	10/4	39	22.5		iAUC
Oh2014	T2D	Korean subjects	16	9/7	54	24.4	56.4	iAUC
Ostoff2014	NGT		9	4/5	41	24		tAUC
Plamboeck2013	NGT		10	10/0	67	25		iAUC
Pontikis2011	NGT		10	0/10	25.3	25		tAUC
Rhee2014	NGT		10	4/6	40	24		tAUC
Vardarli2011	T2D		21	18/3	59	28.6	72	iAUC
Vardarli2014	T2D		20	16/4	59	30.6	60	iAUC
Villareal2010	NGT	Low risk genetic variants	10	2/8	44.8	31.9		tAUC

¹NGT, normal glucose tolerance; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; T2D, type 2 diabetes.

²Specific characteristics of the subject group. T1D, type 1 diabetes; GDM: gestational diabetes mellitus; LAGB, laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding; RYGB, Roux-en-Y gastric bypass; GPB, gastric bypass; SAGB, single anastomosis gastric bypass; SG: sleeve gastrectomy;

³Incretin effect calculated using total (absolute) AUCs (tAUC) or incremental AUCs (iAUC).

Table S6. Variables extracted from the NGT and T2D subject groups, number of subject groups with available values (N) and summary statistics. Only variables reported in 40 subject groups or more are considered (except for T2D-specific variables).

Variable	N	Statistics ¹
Number of subjects	74	10 [6-39]
Sex (F%) ²	64	45 [0-100]
Age (years)	74	44.6 [16.0-67.0]
BMI (kg/m ²)	74	25.8 [20.2-45.1]
Glucose tolerance	74	NGT (48), T2D (26)
OGTT dose (g)	74	50 (41), 75 (33)
Test duration (min) ³	74	240 (40), 180 (34)
IE method ⁴	74	tAUC (39), iAUC (35)
IE from insulin (%)	68	53.4 [5.0-96.0]
IE from insulin SD (%)	68	18.3 [4.0-50.6]
IE from C-peptide (%)	59	45.7 [-8.8-78.6]
IE from C-peptide SD (%)	59	17.0 [4.0-57.8]
HbA1c (%)	55	5.6 [4.7-10.0]
Fasting glucose (mmol/L)	73	5.3 [4.0-12.8]
Fasting insulin (nmol/L)	68	0.068 [0.020-0.246]
Fasting C-peptide (nmol/L)	53	0.70 [0.30-1.77]
Glucose iAUC mean (mmol/L) ⁵	67	1.53 [0.45-5.95]
Insulin iAUC mean (nmol/L) ^{5,6}	65	0.159 [0.027-0.491]
C-peptide iAUC mean (nmol/L) ⁵	42	0.86 [0.15-1.70]
Fasting GIP (pmol/L) ⁶	53	11.3 [4.0-35.0]
Fasting GLP-1 (pmol/L) ⁶	56	8.9 [1.5-27.0]
GIP iAUC mean (pmol/L) ⁶	51	23.7 [6.3-42.5]
GLP-1 iAUC mean (pmol/L) ⁶	55	2.5 [-0.8-10.8]
T2D duration (months) ⁷	22	53.5 [8.0-90.0]
Age at T2D diagnosis (years) ⁷	22	63 [0-100]
T2D medication use (%) ^{7,8}	74	10 [6-39]

¹median [min-max] for numeric variables or category (n) for categorical variables.

²Percentage of females on the total number of subjects.

³One subject group with 120 min duration was pooled with the 180 min group; two subject groups with 210 min duration and one subject group with 300 min duration were pooled with the 240 min group.

⁴IE calculated from total AUC (tAUC) or incremental AUC (iAUC).

⁵iAUC means are calculated as explained in Methods.

⁶Some outliers excluded (see Supplementary Methods).

⁷Data in T2D subjects only.

⁸Percentage of subjects using diabetes medications.

Table S7. Four groups of studies for meta-regression of IE from insulin. A subject group from the selected studies was included in one of the listed groups (A1, A2, B1 or B2) only if values were reported for all the variables characterizing the group (marked with “x” in the table).

Variable	Group of studies			
	A1	A2	B1	B2
Number of subject groups	58	67	36	45
Sex	x		x	
Age	x	x	x	x
BMI	x	x	x	x
Glucose tolerance	x	x	x	x
Fasting glucose	x	x	x	x
OGTT dose	x	x	x	x
Test duration	x	x	x	x
IE method	x	x	x	x
Fasting GIP			x	x
GIP iAUC mean			x	x
Fasting GLP-1			x	x
GLP-1 iAUC mean			x	x
Insulin iAUC mean			x	x

Table S8. Meta-analysis of the difference in IE calculated from insulin between T2D and NGT subjects, adjusted for a single covariate. Sex (as female proportion), age and BMI used in the adjustment are mean values in NGT and T2D subjects or the difference between the means of the two groups. Table cells show the significance level of each variable (based on metafor), separately considered in the adjusted meta-analysis model for IE from insulin (IEins, N=16) and C-peptide (IEcpep, N=17).

Variable	IEins	IEcpep
Sex difference	0.51	0.29
Age difference	0.20	0.18
BMI difference	0.57	0.79
OGTT dose	0.054	0.15
Sex ¹	0.21	0.97
Age	0.0026	0.040
BMI	0.86	0.54

¹N=12 for IE from insulin and N=13 for IE from C-peptide, as sex was missing in some studies.

Table S9. Selection of significant meta-regression predictors of IE from insulin using backward variable elimination in Groups A.

Group	Method	Selected variables ¹	Order of variable removal ¹
A1 (N=58)	metafor	Gtol (<0.0001), BMI (0.0046)	age (0.71), sex (0.49), FG (0.40), IE method (0.49), DUR (0.10), OGTT dose (0.10)
	metaLik	Gtol (<0.0001)	age (0.90), Basal glucose (0.40), OGTT dose (0.27), IE method (0.30), sex (0.26), BMI (0.069), DUR (0.056)
A2 (N=67)	metafor	Gtol (<0.0001), BMI (0.0046)	age (0.89), FG (0.39), IE method (0.29), DUR (0.22), OGTT dose (0.075)
	metaLik	Gtol (<0.0001)	age (0.67), FG (0.36), OGTT dose (0.23), IE method (0.24), DUR (0.12), BMI (0.062)

¹p value in parenthesis. Gtol: glucose tolerance; FG: fasting glucose; DUR: test duration.

Table S10. Selection of significant meta-regression predictors of IE from insulin using information criteria in Groups A. The table shows the top three models classified according the small-sample corrected Akaike information criterion (AICC).

Group A1 (N=58)		Group A2 (N=67)	
Selected variables ¹	AICC	Selected variables ¹	AICC
Gtol, BMI, DUR	487.3	Gtol, BMI, DUR	566.6
Gtol, BMI, DUR, sex	487.9	Gtol, BMI	567.2
Gtol, BMI, DUR, IE method	488.6	Gtol, BMI, IE method	567.3

¹Gtol: glucose tolerance; FG: fasting glucose; DUR: test duration.

Table S11. Meta-regression models for IE from C-peptide in Group A2 and B2. Table cells show the significance level of the variables in a multivariable model based on metafor. IE from C-peptide is reported in a smaller number of studies, compared to insulin.

Variable ¹	Group A2 (N=58) ²	Group B2 (N=37) ²
Gtol	<0.0001	<0.0001
BMI	0.068	0.0028
FGIP	-	0.038

¹Gtol: glucose tolerance; FGIP: fasting GIP.

Table S12. Selection of significant meta-regression predictors of IE from insulin using backward variable elimination in Groups B.

Group	Method	Selected variables ¹	Order of variable removal ¹
B1 (N=36)	metafor	BMI (0.0001), DUR (0.0054), FG (<0.0001), FGIP (0.011)	sex (0.89), FGLP-1 (0.80), Gtol (0.61), iAUCins (0.48), OGTT dose (0.59), iAUCGLP-1 (0.39), IE method (0.22), Age (0.096), iAUCGIP (0.16)
	metaLik	BMI (<0.0001), DUR (0.001), FGIP (0.0001)	sex (0.85), Gtol (0.63), FGLP-1 (0.45), IE method (0.42), OGTT dose (0.37), iAUCins (0.37), iAUCGLP-1 (0.34), iAUCGIP (0.075), FG (0.24), age (0.27)
B2 (N=45)	metafor	iAUCins (0.0001), FG (<0.0001), OGTT dose (0.027)	FGLP-1 (0.91), BMI (0.90), iAUCGLP-1 (0.61), IE method (0.49), iAUCGIP (0.35), DUR (0.35), Gtol (0.20), age (0.091), FGIP (0.18)
	metaLik	FG (< 0.0001)	IE method (0.91), Gtol (0.78), DUR (0.56), OGTT dose (0.28), iAUCGLP-1 (0.37), iAUCins (0.50), iAUCGIP (0.27), Age (0.29), FGLP-1 (0.36), FGIP (0.19), BMI (0.089)

¹p value in parenthesis. Gtol: glucose tolerance; FG: fasting glucose; DUR: test duration; FGIP: fasting GIP; FGLP-1: fasting GLP-1; iAUCins: insulin iAUC mean; iAUCGLP-1: GLP-1 iAUC mean.

Table S13. Selection of significant meta-regression predictors of IE from insulin using information criteria in Groups B. The table shows the top three models classified according the small-sample corrected Akaike information criterion (AICC).

Group B1 (N=36)		Group B2 (N=45)	
Selected variables ¹	AICC	Selected variables ¹	AICC
BMI, DUR, FGIP	296.7	FG, iAUCGLP-1	379.9
BMI, DUR, FGIP, FG	297.8	BMI, Gtol, FGIP	380.2
BMI, DUR, FGIP, iAUCins	297.9	BMI, FG, FGIP	380.4

¹Gtol: glucose tolerance; FG: fasting glucose; DUR: test duration; iAUCins: insulin iAUC mean; FGIP: fasting GIP; iAUCGLP-1: GLP-1 iAUC mean.

Table S14. Meta-regression models of IE from insulin, including glucose tolerance, BMI and a single additional variable, shown in the table heading. Table cells show the significance level (from metafor) of the variables, except for the last table row, which shows the number of subject groups.

Variable ¹	FGIP	iAUCins	iAUCGLP-1
Gtol	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
BMI	0.0011	0.013	0.026
Additional variable	0.031	0.90	0.18
Number of subject groups	50	63	52

¹Gtol: glucose tolerance; FGIP: fasting GIP; iAUCins: insulin iAUC mean; iAUCGLP-1: GLP-1 iAUC mean.

Table S15. Meta-regression of IE from insulin in the T2D subjects of Group A2 (N=25). Table cells show the significance level of the variable.

Variable	metafor	metaLik
BMI	0.51	0.34
OGTT dose	<0.0001	0.005

Table S16. Meta-regression of IE from insulin in the T2D subjects of Group A2 including T2D-specific variables (N=21 or 22). Table cells show the significance level of the variable in the meta-regression model including the OGTT dose and one of the listed variables.

Variable	metafor	metaLik
Duration of T2D	0.15	0.72
Age at T2D diagnosis	0.25	0.56
Use of antidiabetic medications	0.38	0.42

Table S17. Meta-analysis of the difference between IE calculated from insulin and IE calculated from C-peptide, adjusted for a single covariate, in all subject groups (N=55; N=54 for fasting glucose). Table cells show the significance level of each variable, separately considered in the adjusted meta-analysis model.

Variable	metafor
OGTT dose	0.44
IE method	0.12
Glucose tolerance	0.037
Fasting glucose	0.048
BMI	0.095

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Relationship between IE calculated from absolute or incremental insulin AUCs in 75 subjects from Refs 7-9 of the Supplementary Methods. Glucose tolerance is according to the ADA 1997 criteria.

Figure S2. Correlation matrix between the variables considered in the study. Variables are listed in Table S1. The matrix shows the Pearson's correlation coefficient and the color scale highlights the strength and the direction of the correlation.

Figure S3. Weighted mean difference (WMD) between T2D and NGT subjects in IE calculated from C-peptide (IEcpep), depicted as a forest plot including all studies testing the difference. A negative difference indicates lower IE in T2D. The blue diamond represents the overall WMD with the 95% confidence interval. The green squares with the horizontal lines represent WMD with the 95% confidence interval for each study.

Figure S4. Sex (as female proportion), age and BMI in the studies comparing IE in NGT and T2D subjects. The identity line is shown in each panel.

Figure S5. Relationship between mean age in NGT and T2D subjects and the difference between the two groups in IE calculated from insulin (IEins). The figure includes the studies with matched T2D and NGT subjects, shown in the forest plot of Figure 2 in the main text. The color indicates the OGTT dose (in grams).

Figure S6. Relationship between IE calculated from insulin and fasting glucose in all studies.

Figure S7. Relationship between IE calculated from insulin (IEins) and fasting GIP. Dots filled in black indicate GIP values obtained from old assays after being rescaled as described in the Supplementary Methods.

Figure S8. IE calculated from insulin (IEins) in T2D subjects, plotted according to the OGTT glucose dose (in grams).

Figure S9. Bland-Altman plot of the incretin effect from insulin (IEins) and C-peptide (IEcpep).

Figure S10. Meta-analysis funnel plots and Egger test p value. Difference between T2D and NGT in IE calculated from insulin (top, $p=0.062$) and from C-peptide (middle, $p=0.007$). Bottom: difference between IE calculated from insulin and C-peptide in all studies ($p=0.66$).

Figure S11. IE calculated from insulin in the studies with matched T2D and NGT subjects, shown in the forest plot of Figure 2 in the main text. The dotted line is the identity line.

